

AN ALTERNATIVE EXPLANATION OF ENTANGLED ELECTRONS WITHIN REALISM AND LOCALITY PRINCIPLES

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an alternative interpretation of quantum entanglement, suggesting that a single combination of opposite spins accounts for experimental observations. By drawing analogies between macroscopic two-dimensional (2D) structures and intrinsic electron properties, we present a geometric framework that preserves realism and locality without invoking non-local interactions. This approach challenges conventional interpretations and seeks to provide a more intuitive understanding of entangled systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Mathematical Influence on Physics

The evolution of mathematical concepts has played a pivotal role in advancing physics. Mathematical theories and models have enabled scientists to predict physical phenomena with remarkable accuracy and to uncover intricate relationships between physical quantities and parameters. This observation prompts a fundamental question: **Is our universe inherently mathematical, and does the pursuit of mathematics equate to an understanding of the physical world?** Contrary to appearing purely philosophical, this inquiry delves into the core of scientific methodology and the nature of reality.

Mathematics can be metaphorically described as an extensive toolkit that physicists utilize to model and interpret real-world phenomena. The breadth of mathematical tools available ensures that, given sufficient attempts, a suitable model can be identified to describe a particular physical system. These models not only provide accurate representations of observed phenomena but can also be extended to similar systems, often revealing underlying universal principles (Wigner, 1960).

However, several critical considerations must be addressed:

- 1. Non-Intuitive Correspondence:** Mathematical models do not always intuitively align with the physical systems they aim to describe. The internal structures and mechanisms of these models may bear little resemblance to the actual physical processes (Hamming, 1980).
- 2. Multiplicity of Models:** Multiple mathematical frameworks can be applicable to the same physical phenomenon, each offering different perspectives and insights (Tegmark, 2008).
- 3. Potential for Misinterpretation:** Relying solely on the success of a particular mathematical model to infer the true mechanisms of a physical system can lead to significant misinterpretations and distortions of reality (Laughlin & Pines, 2000).

To illustrate these points, consider the field of machine learning, specifically the use of neural networks and decision trees for function approximation.

1.2. Neural Networks and Decision Trees in Function Approximation

Neural Networks are computational models inspired by the human brain's architecture. They consist of interconnected layers of neurons that can learn to approximate complex functions through training on large datasets (Goodfellow *et al.*, 2016). For example, training a neural network to learn the function $Y = X^2$ involves providing numerous input-output pairs. The network adjusts its internal weights to minimize the

error between its predictions and the actual values, ultimately predicting Y for any given X with high accuracy, comparable to precise calculator computations.

Decision Trees are another machine learning tool that models decisions and their possible consequences in a tree-like structure (Breiman *et al.*, 1984). The tree learns a series of decision rules based on input data to accurately produce the square of any given X . Similar to neural networks, decision trees can predict Y with high accuracy. The logic, mechanisms, and internal rules of the decision tree are entirely distinct from the mathematical concept of squaring or the architecture of a neural network, yet both models achieve precise computations of the square.

These examples raise critical questions:

- **Do neural networks or decision trees uncover any intrinsic, hidden properties of the mathematical function $Y = X^2$?**
- **Can we erroneously conclude that the physical square inherently contains a specific number of interconnected neurons or resembles a multi-level tree structure based on the performance of these models?**

The answer is negative. While these models can approximate the function accurately, their internal workings do not reflect the true nature of the mathematical operation they represent.

Mathematics undoubtedly offers a vast and versatile toolkit capable of modelling an extensive range of phenomena. Regardless of the complexity or diversity of data and results, there exists a mathematical framework that can derive comprehensive functions from the available information, often providing multiple viable solutions. This omnipresence of applicable mathematical tools means that a suitable model will invariably be found to describe any given set of data.

However, this capability introduces a significant caveat: **the presence of a mathematical solution does not necessarily imply a direct correspondence with physical reality.** Mathematical models serve as proxies or representations, rather than direct mappings of physical mechanisms (Cartwright, 1983). Therefore, relying solely on mathematical models—embodied in the adage "Shut up and calculate!"—can lead to the misconception that understanding mathematics equates to understanding the physical world.

To achieve a more profound understanding of the universe, it is imperative to go beyond mathematical modelling and develop methodologies that can directly probe and elucidate the intrinsic properties of physical phenomena. Mathematics provides the language and tools for description and prediction, but the key to truly comprehending the universe lies in uncovering the underlying physical principles that these mathematical models represent.

2. QUANTUM ENTANGLEMENT OF TWO ELECTRONS

2.1. Quantum Entanglement and the Singlet State

Quantum mechanics introduces phenomena that defy classical intuition, among which **quantum entanglement** stands out as one of the most intriguing and fundamental. Quantum entanglement is a physical phenomenon where two or more particles become interconnected such that the state of one instantly influences the state of the other(s), regardless of the distance separating them (Einstein *et al.*, 1935). This connection persists even if the entangled particles are light-years apart, a feature that Einstein famously referred to as "spooky action at a distance."

The **wave function** describes the quantum state of a system. For two entangled electrons in the **singlet state**, the wave function is given by:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_A|\downarrow\rangle_B - |\downarrow\rangle_A|\uparrow\rangle_B)$$

Where:

- $|\uparrow\rangle_A$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_A$ denote electron *A* having spin up or down, respectively.
- $|\uparrow\rangle_B$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_B$ denote electron *B* having spin up or down, respectively.

The singlet state is a superposition where the spins are **anti-correlated**. If one electron is measured to have spin up, the other must be spin down, and vice versa. The singlet state is **rotationally invariant**, meaning that no matter how you rotate your coordinate system, the entanglement property remains intact (Sakurai & Napolitano, 1995).

In quantum mechanics, measurement affects the system being observed. When measuring the spin of an electron along a particular axis (e.g., the z-axis), the electron's spin state "collapses" to either spin up or spin down with probabilities determined by the wave function. This instantaneous correlation challenges our classical notions of locality.

2.2. Bell's Inequalities

In 1964, physicist **John Bell** formulated **Bell's inequalities** to test whether the predictions of quantum mechanics regarding entanglement could be explained by any **local hidden variable theories**—theories that assume properties (hidden variables) determine outcomes and that no influence can travel faster than light (locality) (Bell, 1964).

Bell's inequalities set an upper limit on the strength of correlations between entangled particles as predicted by local hidden variable theories. If experiments violate Bell's inequalities, it suggests that no local hidden variable theory can fully explain quantum entanglement, supporting the non-local nature of quantum mechanics.

For simplicity, consider the **CHSH (Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt) form** of Bell's inequality, which involves measurements along different axes (Clauser *et al.*, 1969):

$$|S| = |E(a, b) - E(a, b') + E(a', b) + E(a', b')| \leq 2$$

Where:

- $E(a, b)$ is the expectation value of the product of spin measurements along axes *a* and *b*.

- a and a' are two different measurement settings for electron *A*.
- b and b' are two different measurement settings for electron *B*.

Quantum mechanics predicts that for certain choices of measurement axes, the value of $|S|$ can exceed 2, reaching up to $2 \times \sqrt{2}$ (approximately 2.828). This **violation** of Bell's inequality has been confirmed by numerous experiments, thereby ruling out local hidden variable theories (Aspect *et al.*, 1982).

3. INCUMBENT INTERPRETATIONS

In 2022, the Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded jointly to **Alain Aspect**, **John F. Clauser**, and **Anton Zeilinger** for their groundbreaking experiments with entangled photons. Their work fundamentally challenged classical notions by demonstrating the violation of Bell's inequalities, providing compelling evidence against **local realism**—the belief that particles possess definite properties (realism) and that information cannot travel faster than light (locality) (The Nobel Prize in Physics 2022).

While the Nobel laureates primarily conducted experiments demonstrating the fundamental non-classical nature of quantum mechanics, their subsequent interpretations offer insights into alternatives to realism and locality.

Zeilinger (1999) suggests that **information** is not merely a description of reality but a fundamental building block. This shifts the focus from particles possessing inherent properties to the information generated through interactions and measurements. This approach emphasizes the operations (measurements) performed on quantum systems rather than the underlying reality of those systems (Zeilinger, 1999).

Contextuality posits that the outcome of a measurement depends on the specific set of measurements being performed, challenging the notion that particles have predefined properties independent of measurement contexts (Kochen & Specker, 1967).

Relational Quantum Mechanics (Rovelli, 1996) proposes that the properties of quantum systems are relative to the observer.

QBism (Quantum Bayesianism) (Fuchs & Schack, 2013) treats quantum probabilities as subjective degrees of belief, emphasizing the role of the observer in defining the quantum state. This interpretation moves away from realism by denying that quantum states represent objective reality.

4. A NON-SPOOKY INTERPRETATION

4.1. Geometric Analogy of Electron Spin

Quantum entanglement challenges classical notions of realism and locality, particularly through the violation of Bell's inequalities. Traditional interpretations often require abandoning one of these principles to explain the observed correlations. Here, we present a geometric analogy that maintains both realism and locality by positing a singular combination of opposite spins as the underlying mechanism.

4.1.1. Macroscopic Two-Dimensional Structures

Many macroscopic objects, despite existing in three-dimensional (3D) space, can be effectively modelled as predominantly two-dimensional (2D) structures:

- **Solar System:** Planetary orbits lie within the relatively flat ecliptic plane (Prialnik, 2000).
- **Milky Way Galaxy:** Exhibits a flat spiral disk structure (Binney & Tremaine, 2008).
- **Massive Black Holes:** Observed to expand in diameter and volume consistent with disk-like or coin-shaped geometries rather than spherical growth (Kormendy & Richstone, 1995).

These objects possess extremely high mass densities and consistent rotational motion.

4.1.2. Electrons as 2D Entities

Electrons, fundamental particles with intrinsic spin, also exhibit high mass densities and rotational characteristics. While the origin of electron spin differs fundamentally from macroscopic rotation, for analytical purposes, we model electrons as 2D disk-like entities rather than 3D spheres (Griffiths & Schroeter, 2018). In a 2D framework, an object's spin can manifest in two discrete directions: **clockwise** or **counterclockwise**.

4.1.3. Representation in 2D Space

In 2D space, spin states can be represented by two symmetric points equidistant from a central axis, separated by a distance of 2 units. This configuration aligns with Bell's inequalities, which constrain the maximum correlation distance to 2 units in 2D space. The perpendicular orientation of these points relative to the measurement axis ensures a direct, non-influential correlation between spin states, avoiding the "spooky action at a distance" paradox.

4.2. Extension to Three Dimensions and Bell's Inequality Violation

Because quantum measurements are taken in 3D space, the geometric analogy requires adjustment:

- **3D Representation:** Consider two circles, each with a radius of 1 unit, positioned 1 unit away from both sides of the measurement axis. These circles function as "clocks," where the hands indicate spin projections along the measurement axis.
- **Observation of Entangled Particles:** Observations yield opposite spin combinations, such as 12 o'clock and 6 o'clock or 3 o'clock and 9 o'clock. Connecting these points forms lines with lengths of $2 \times \sqrt{2}$ units, exceeding the classical Bell inequality limit of 2 units and thereby demonstrating its violation within this geometric framework.

This model maintains locality by attributing the observed correlations to geometric relationships rather than non-local interactions.

4.3. Addressing Probabilistic Nature Through Machine Learning Analogy

A potential critique of this geometric analogy is its simplification of the probabilistic nature inherent in quantum

measurements. To address this, consider a **machine learning (ML) model** trained to distinguish between cats and dogs based on observable features like whiskers, paws, and tails. The model assigns probabilities p (cat) and $1 - p$ (dog) to each classification. A well-trained model ensures that both probabilities lie within the interval $(0,1)$, reflecting uncertainty similar to quantum superpositions (Bishop, 2006).

- **Before Measurement:** The model cannot definitively classify an object, akin to an electron existing in a superposition of spin states.
- **Upon Measurement:** The model's prediction collapses to a definite classification, mirroring the wave function collapse in quantum mechanics.
- **Entangled Pair Analogy:** In an entangled cat-dog pair, measuring one object (e.g., observing a cat) instantaneously determines the state of the other (the dog), analogous to entangled quantum states.

This analogy illustrates that quantum entanglement can be understood without abandoning realism or locality, provided more realistic assumptions about the underlying mechanisms are adopted.

5. CONCLUSION

The analogies presented in this study may not fully correspond to the observed physical phenomena, but they emphasize the importance of upholding fundamental principles in our theoretical frameworks. Historically, unexplained phenomena were often attributed to divine intervention. With the advent of quantum mechanics, our perception of reality shifted towards a probabilistic interpretation. While this probabilistic worldview may accurately describe aspects of the quantum realm, the dismissal of foundational principles such as realism and locality — cornerstones of modern physics — should be approached with caution.

Modern physical theories prioritize simplicity and aesthetic elegance, primarily through robust mathematical formulations (Chandrasekhar, 1987). In contrast, the explanations proposed by the 2022 Nobel laureates, while empirically validated, lack the simplicity and aesthetic appeal valued in theoretical physics. Consequently, it is essential to explore more straightforward and intuitive explanations before resorting to complex modifications of established principles.

Consider systems comprising two objects exhibiting opposite properties regardless of the distance separating them. To preserve locality, it is necessary to limit the number of possible property states. Analogous to the two sides of a coin or a pair of gloves, each object can exist in one of two distinct states. Measuring one object's state instantaneously determines the state of its counterpart without necessitating any form of information exchange or "connection" across space. This perspective suggests that the underlying mechanism governing these correlations does not require the invocation of non-local interactions.

The explanation we propose diverges from the concept of hidden variables, offering a distinct yet plausible alternative. By maintaining the integrity of realism and locality, this approach seeks to provide a more intuitive and conceptually straightforward understanding of quantum entanglement and the associated violations of Bell's inequalities.

In summary, while quantum mechanics has undeniably advanced our comprehension of the microscopic world, it remains essential to critically evaluate and explore simpler explanatory models that adhere to fundamental physical principles. Such endeavours not only enhance our theoretical understanding but also preserve the elegant simplicity that has long been a guiding principle in the development of physical theories.

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